

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE ATTITUDE OF STANDARD PROTOCOL ON PAEIRATRIC WARD AMONG STAFF NURSE IN SMVMCH AT PUDUCHERRY

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: A standard operating procedure (SOP) SOPs as "detailed, written instructions to achieve uniformity of the performance of a specific function". SOPs usually get applied in pharmaceutical processing and for related clinical studies. **Objectives of the study:** To assess the attitude of standard protocol on paediatric ward among staff nurse. To associate the attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse with selected their selected demographic variables. **Methodology:** The total number of 30 staff nurse were selected for this study. The standard protocol was assessed by using Likert scale. The study had assessed and proved that attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse were categorized in the interpretation. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** The result of this present study is that, out of 30 samples 93.3% were in favourable, 6.7% were in moderately favourable none of them in unfavourable in following the standard protocol. Mean and standard deviation regarding attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse in SMVMCH, at Puducherry. The mean score is 137.53 with the standard deviation of 17.85. **Conclusion:** The study revealed that staff nurse is favourably practicing the standard protocol on paediatric ward which is assess with Likert scale and it's suggested to go for some standard practice to improve the quality of nursing care

Keywords: Attitude, Pediatric ward, Staff nurse, Standard protocol

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Introduction

A standard operating procedure (SOP) is a set of step-by-step instructions compiled by an organization to help workers carry out routine operations. SOPs aim to achieve efficiency, quality output, and uniformity of performance, while reducing miscommunication and failure to comply with industry regulations.

Some military services (e.g., in the U.S. and the UK) use the term standing (rather than standard) operating procedure, since a military SOP refers to a unit's unique procedures, which are not necessarily standard to another unit. The word "standard" could suggest that only one (standard) procedure is to be used across all units.

The term is sometimes used facetiously to refer to practices that are unconstructive, yet the norm. In the Philippines, for instance, "SOP" is the terms for pervasive corruption within the government and its institutions.

International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) defines SOPs as "detailed, written instructions to achieve uniformity of the performance of a specific function". SOPs usually get applied in pharmaceutical processing and for related clinical studies. There the focus is always set on repeated application of unchanged processes and procedures and its documentation, hence supporting the segregation of origins, causes and effects. Further application is with triage, when limited resources get used according to an assessment on for SOPs. The Quality Assurance Unit are individuals who are responsible for monitoring whether the study report and tests are meeting the SOP.

Objectives

- To assess the attitude of standard protocol on paediatric ward among staff nurse.
- To associate the attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse with selected theirselected demographic variables.

Methodology

The research approach chosen for this study is Quantitative descriptive evaluative research approach. The research design chosen for this study is Descriptive research design. The study was planned in paediatric ward in SMVMCH, at Puducherry. The population for the study includes all staff nurse who are working in SMVMCH. The sample selected for the present study comprises of staff nurses working in Paediatric ward. The size of the sample of 30 staff nurse working in paediatric ward. Purposive sampling technique.

Inclusion criteria

- All nurses working in paediatric ward in SMVMCH.
- Registered GNM / B.SC., nursing.

Exclusion criteria

- Staff nurses who are not working in paediatric ward

Result and Findings:**Table 1: Frequency and percentage wise distribution of demographic variables among staff nurse.**

SL. NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Age		
	a) 20 to 30	28	93.3
	b) 31 to 40	2	6.7
	c) 41 to 50	0	0
	d) 51 to 60	0	0
2	Gender		
	a) Male	3	10
	b) Female	27	90
3	Qualification		
	a) ANM	0	0
	b) GNM	2	6.7
	c) B.Sc.,nursing	28	93.3
	d) M.Sc.,nursing	0	0
4	Year of experience		
	a) 1 years	11	36.7
	b) 2 to 4 years	16	53.3
	c) 5 to 10 years	2	6.7
	d) Above 10 years	1	3.3
5	Religion		
	a) Hindu	29	96.7
	b) Christian	1	3.3
	c) Muslim	0	0
6	Monthly income		
	a) 8000 to 10000	7	23.3
	b) 10000 to 12000	13	43.3
	c) 12000 to 15000	9	30
	d) Above 15000	1	3.4
7	Marital status		
	a) Married	11	36.7
	b) Unmarried	19	63.3
8	Residential area		
	a) Urban	12	40
	b) Rural	18	60
9	Type of family		
	a) Joint family	6	20
	b) Nuclear family	24	80
10	Financial status		
	a) Middle class	17	56.7
	b) Upper class	0	0
	c) Lower class	13	43.3
	d) Poor class	0	0

Table 1 shows frequency and Percentage wise distribution of demographic variables among staff nurse. Out of the 30 staff nurse who were interviewed, Majority of the staff nurse 28(93.3%) of study population were in the age group are 20-30 years. Majority of the staff nurse were female 27(90%). Majority of the staff nurse were B.Sc. Nursing 28(93.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were 2 to 4 years of experience 16(53.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were Hindu 29(96.7%). Majority of the staff nurse Monthly Income were 13(43.3%) Rs 10000 to 12000. Majority of the staff nurse were Unmarried 19(63.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were Rural 18(60%). Majority of the staff nurse were Nuclear family 24(80%). Majority of the staff nurse were Middle class 17(56.7%) respectively.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage wise distribution of level of attitude of standard protocol on pediatric ward among staff nurse.

LEVEL OF ATTITUDE	FREQUENCY (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
UNFAVOURABLE (1-50)	0	0
MODERATELY FAVOURABLE (51-100)	2	6.7
FAVOURABLE (101-150)	28	93.3
TOTAL	30	100
MEAN ± STANDARD DEVIATION	137.53 ± 17.85	

The above table reveals that majority of the staff nurse were B.Sc. Nursing 28(93.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were 2 to 4 years of experience 16(53.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were Hindu 29(96.7%). Majority of the staff nurse Monthly Income were 13(43.3%) Rs 10000 to 12000. Majority of the staff nurse were Unmarried 19(63.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were Rural 18(60%). Majority of the staff nurse were Nuclear family 24(80%). Majority of the staff nurse were Middle class 17(56.7%) respectively. Frequency and percentage-wise distribution of level of awareness of staff nurses regarding hazardous chemicals. The finding revealed that majority, 22 (73.3%) of the staff nurses had moderate level of awareness and 8 (26.7%) of the staff nurses had adequate level of awareness regarding hazardous chemicals.

Table 3: Association between the level of attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse with selected their selected demographic variables.

SL. NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	LEVEL OF ATTITUDE				Chi-square X ² and P-Value
		MODERATE		FAVOURABLE		
		N	%	N	%	
1	Age					X ² =0.153 Df=1 p =0.696 NS
	a) 20 to 30	2	100	26	92.9	
	b) 31 to 40	0	0	2	7.1	
	c) 41 to 50	0	0	0	0	
	d) 51 to 60	0	0	0	0	
2	Gender					X ² =3.81 Df=1 p =0.05 *S
	a) Male	1	50	2	7.1	
	b) Female	1	50	26	92.9	
3	Qualification					X ² =6.46 Df=1 p =0.011 *S
	a) ANM	0	0	0	0	
	b) GNM	1	50	1	3.6	
	c) B.Sc.,nursing	1	50	27	96.4	
	d) M.Sc.,nursing	0	0	0	0	
4	Year of experience					X ² =0.323 Df=3 p =0.956 NS
	a) 1 years	1	50	10	35.7	
	b) 2 to 4 years	1	50	15	53.6	
	c) 5 to 10 years	0	0	2	7.1	
	d) Above 10 years	0	0	1	3.6	
5	Religion					X ² =0.074 Df=1 p =0.786 NS
	a) Hindu	2	100	27	96.4	
	b) Christian	0	0	1	3.6	
	c) Muslim	0	0	0	0	
6	Monthly income					X ² =1.38 Df=3 p =0.708 NS
	a) 8000 to 10000	1	50	6	21.4	
	b) 10000 to 12000	1	50	12	42.9	
	c) 12000 to 15000	0	0	9	32.1	
	d) Above 15000	0	0	1	3.6	
7	Marital status					X ² =0.164

	a) Married	1	50	10	35.7	Df=1 p =0.685 NS
	b) Unmarried	1	50	18	64.3	
8	Residential area					X ² =0.089 Df=1 p =0.765 NS
	a) Urban	1	50	11	39.3	
	b) Rural	1	50	17	60.7	
9	Type of family					X ² =0.652 Df=2 p =0.722 NS
	a) Joint family	0	0	6	21.4	
	b) Nuclear family	2	10 0	22	78.6	
10	Financial status					X ² =0.039 Df=1 p =0.844 NS
	a) Middle class	1	50	16	57.1	
	b) Upper class	0	0	0	0	
	c) Lower class	1	50	12	42.9	
	d) Poor class	0	0	0	0	

***-p < 0.05 significant, *-p < 0.001 highly significant, NS-Non significance**

The table 3 depicts that the demographic variable, Gender and Qualification had shown statistically significant association between the levels of attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse with selected their selected demographic variables. The other demographic variable had not shown statistically significant association between the level of attitude of standard protocol among staff nurse with selected their selected demographic variables respectively

Discussion

The main focus of the study was conducted to assess the attitude of standard protocol on paediatric ward among staff nurse in smvmch, at Puducherry. Total numbers of 30 staff nurse were selected for the study. The the attitude was assessed on 5 point likert scale. The study had assessed and prove the attitude regarding the standard protocol among staff nurse. Out of the 30 staff nurse who were interviewed, Majority of the staff nurse 28(93.3%) of study population were in the age group are 20-30 years. Majority of the staff nurse were female 27(90%). Majority of the staff nurse were B.Sc.,nursing 28(93.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were 2 to 4 years of experience 16(53.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were Hindu 29(96.7%). Majority of the staff nurse Monthly Income were 13(43.3%) Rs 10000 to 12000. Majority of the staff nurse were Unmarried 19(63.3%). Majority of the staff nurse were Rural 18(60%). Majority of the staff nurse were Nuclear family 24(80%). Majority of the staff nurse were Middle class 17(56.7%) respectively.

The following study is supported for the first objectives of the present study by **Arkadeep Dhali, et.al 2021.**, Standard operating procedure for paediatric inpatient care in a public general hospital in rural South India: a quality improvement project, Methods are a series of interventions were implemented and assessed using plan-do-study-act (PDSA) cycles. The findings from the PDSA cycle of a previous intervention were used to implement change in the next intervention. Results of the study, At the end of 3 months, improvement was noted with the increase in the bed occupancy rate by 22%. Conclusion we were able to implement an SOP and bring a significant improvement in the quality of care provided.

Conclusion

This implies on the content of the study investigator have assessed the attitude of standard protocol on paediatric ward have practiced favourably level of attitude with assessing the standard protocol and some are moderately favourable on assessment of standard protocol. In this study the investigator finds that the staff nurse working in paediatric ward favourable following the standard protocol. During the data collection I assessed that staff nurse have moderately favourable in following the standard protocol due insufficiency of staff nurse, and time and doctors rounds. Staff nurse in the paediatric ward are included in the study samples and analysed using standard protocol. Overall, the tool is useful and effective in determining the outcome of standard protocol.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Some specific research can be carried out in future such as,

- Similar study can be conducted in various hospital.
- The same study can be replicated on a large sample patient.
- A longer period of intervention can be studied for more effectiveness.
- A similar study needs to be conducted in other private and government hospitals order to draw a generalisation.
- A Similar study can be conducted in other parts of the country with a large sample.

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